

I-CLAIM

Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe

Improving Irregular Migrants' Labour Conditions: Agriculture, Food Delivery, and Domestic Work in Europe

Policy Brief

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Summary

Migrants' irregular status in Europe is not a fixed legal category but a product of the interactions between migration, labour and welfare policy regimes. Drawing on research from the Horizon Europe I-CLAIM project, this Policy Brief shows that irregularised migrants occupy positions that are essential. In domestic work, migrants – predominantly women – for example provide indispensable household and personal care across Europe's ageing societies. In agriculture and food delivery, irregularised migrant workers play a crucial role in feeding society.

Apart from being essential, these labour positions are however concentrated in sectors characterised by undeclared work or subcontracting, and as a result suffer from high levels of dependency and labour exploitation. Irregularised workers have limited access to information and support and their access to workers' rights need to be better guaranteed.

Building on research conducted in the Horizon Europe [I-CLAIM project](#), this Policy Brief puts forward the following four policy recommendations for national and EU policymakers

- Expand and improve labour migration and regularisation pathways
- Regulate subcontracting and labour intermediation
- Ensure access to justice and effective complaint mechanisms to all workers, regardless of status
- Ensure access to information and support to irregularised workers

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Introduction

Migrant's irregular status (or 'irregularity') is not a static legal category related merely to migration law and policies. Rather, it is dynamic and produced by intersecting regulatory frameworks and practices governing borders and residence, work, welfare and family life operating at the local, national and EU levels (see [Sigona & van Liempt, 2025](#)). In the [I-CLAIM project](#) irregular migration is conceptualised as a process, not as something static, and as something that is actively produced. The term irregularised migration reflects this conceptualisation and refers to residence and/or employment.

Irregularity impacts individuals unevenly depending on the intersections of nationality, gender, age and generation, socio-economic characteristics, and membership of racialised communities. Our empirical research with irregularised migrants in various European countries found that irregularised migrants occupy positions that are essential. In domestic work, migrants – predominantly women – for example provide indispensable household and personal care across Europe's ageing societies. In agriculture and food delivery, irregularised migrant workers also play a crucial role in producing the food we consume and delivering it on our door.

Apart from being essential, these labour positions are however overlooked within national economies. They are concentrated in activities characterised by informality, a high turnover and subcontracting and suffer from high levels of dependency and labour exploitation. Workers' limited access to remedies, welfare and legal protection reinforces the segmentation of labour markets that are in place.

Building on research conducted in the Horizon Europe [I-CLAIM project](#), this Policy Brief puts forward the following four policy recommendations for national and EU policymakers:

- Expand and improve labour migration and regularisation pathways
- Regulate subcontracting and labour intermediation
- Enforce labour rights and ensure access to complaint mechanisms to all workers, regardless of status
- Ensure access to information and support to irregularised workers

Methodology

This Policy Brief falls within the scope of the [I-CLAIM project](#) which examines the living and labour conditions of irregularised households in Europe. The Policy Brief synthesises the key findings of the Comparative Report on 'Immigration Status and Labour Conditions: Migrant workers in Agriculture, Delivery and Logistics, and Domestic and Care Work in Europe' ([van Liempt et al., 2026](#)), which brings together the cross-cutting findings of the research conducted at the national level in Finland, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland, and the United Kingdom (referred collectively as 'I-CLAIM countries' hereafter; see Annex: I-CLAIM Sector Reports for references to all sector and comparative reports).

The main findings from the national fieldwork and EU-level research were discussed in a series of national stakeholder meetings in the summer and autumn of 2025 and a final EU policy workshop held in Brussels on 13 November 2025. In these meetings, the research teams presented the I-CLAIM findings on irregularity, its production and its effects across different labour sectors (agriculture, delivery and logistics, and domestic and care work), its gender and household dynamics, and racial logics with relevant national and EU stakeholders, including national policymakers, European Commission officials, civil society actors, social partners, practitioners and experts. These consultations informed the policy recommendations included in this Policy Brief as well as two other I-CLAIM Policy briefs, one on gender, households and the production of irregularity in Europe ([Colombi et al. 2026](#)) and one on racial logics of irregular migration (Sigona et al. 2026).

Main research findings

MAIN FINDING #1:

In agricultural work seasonal migration regimes sustain forms of dependency and undeclared work that increase worker's precarity

The agricultural sector is often regulated under norms that govern seasonal work and put temporality central. In spite of the efforts to provide minimum protection mechanisms for seasonal workers (e.g. the 2014 [EU Seasonal Directive](#)) and to penalise unfair employer practices (e.g. the 2009 EU Sanctions Directive), the I-CLAIM research shows that legislation and administrative practices applied in the researched countries generally remain ineffective with regard to seasonal migration and often result in semiformal agreements such as oral agreements instead of written contracts ([Salamena 2025](#)) and earning money informally alongside regular employment ([Merikoski & Näre 2025](#)).

There is an above-average level of undeclared work, job insecurity, forced flexibility, recurring labour exploitation and numerous traps of illegality for migrant agriculture workers in Europe. The social conditionality mechanism introduced as part of [the EU Common Agricultural Policy](#) (CAP) in 2025, which aimed to ensure decent working conditions, has not so far effectively improved the situation of seasonal workers due to minimalist implementation by many member countries and lack of effective inspections. At the heart of seasonal migration policies in agriculture in the countries studied lie numerous commonalities, including a lack of consensus or political will to implement measures ensuring better living and working conditions for migrants with irregular work and residence statuses. Entry channels for seasonal permits often trap migrant workers in conditions of dependency on employers and limited access to social rights.

Apart from working informally or semi-informally and long hours, with insecure and uneven pay, and inadequate housing, there are two other specific concerns around working conditions in this sector that are worth highlighting. First of all, third country national workers from Eastern Europe, North Africa, and Asia often rely on recruiters or intermediaries who mediate access to jobs, accommodation, and transport ([e.g. Matuszczyk 2025](#)). Being dependent on illegal intermediaries particularly increases the risk of exploitation. Second, the often-isolated workplaces in rural areas make migrants particularly vulnerable and exposed to risks, especially for women. The intersection of legal insecurity, workplace power hierarchies and spatial isolation creates conditions in which gender-based violence, harassment and abuse is normalised, underreported and rarely addressed ([Palumbo 2025](#)). Women in agriculture reported frequent experiences of sexual harassment, coercion and unwanted behaviours by employers, supervisors and/or co-workers. These risks were particularly acute in isolated settings such as rural agricultural sites where oversight is limited and reporting mechanisms are weak. The isolated workplace also makes it difficult to access workers' rights more generally and often excludes workers from access to essential infrastructures, such as shops and services, hospitals, support organisations or schools.

MAIN FINDING #2:

In domestic work, employment arrangements are often characterised by differential treatment, low protection and strong dependency on the employer

The domestic work sector is one of the main areas of employment for migrant workers across Europe, especially for female migrants, including those in irregular situations. The sector's specific features—such as its invisibility, the lack of labour inspectorate controls, the personal nature of employer/employee relationships especially in the case of live-in workers as well as the demand for short-term and highly flexible

labour make it into a job opportunity. At the same time, it is exactly the isolation of workers and limited labour inspectorate oversight that contributes to increasing workers' dependency on employers, fostering and perpetuating undeclared work ([ELA 2022](#)) and exploitative working conditions.

While some EU countries, such as the Netherlands ([Hajer & van Liempt 2025](#)) do not have a specific entry route for this sector, others such as Italy ([Marchetti & Lashchuk 2025](#)), Finland ([Merikoski & Näre 2025](#)) and the UK ([Sigona et al. 2025](#)), do. However, a restrictive approach to these policies, together with inadequacies and abuse in their implementation, as in the case of Italy, contributes to increasing domestic workers' situations of vulnerability to undeclared and exploitative work. Various actors – from personal contacts and community networks to recruitment agencies – facilitate the recruitment of migrant domestic workers, often profiting from vulnerabilities created by migration laws and policies.

Inadequacies in national migration policies intersect with gaps in the national labour regulation of the domestic work sector. While Italy and Finland have ratified the ILO's 2011 Domestic Workers Convention No.189, the UK and the Netherlands have not ([van Liempt et al. 2026](#)). Yet, even where specific regulations exist, domestic workers are often treated differently from other workers and enjoy fewer rights – reflecting the ongoing difficulty in recognising reproductive labour as 'real' work. In this context, the devaluation of this type of work and its intimate nature – especially in the live-in arrangements – can enable abuse of power and labour rights violations. [EFFAT](#) has developed a guiding framework for the recognition of domestic work as work.

Many employers are also unaware of their responsibilities and constantly blur the line between professional and personal spheres, while racialised and gendered stereotypes shape hiring practices, and attitudes. These specific conditions also make it hard for workers to negotiate labour conditions and make violations of labour standards and experiences of exploitation and also harassment and gender violence difficult to contest or document.

MAIN FINDING #3:

The food delivery sector with its platform-based business models promote flexibility while transferring costs and risks to workers

Food delivery has become an essential, if marginal, entry point in the European labour market for migrants facing legal and structural barriers in formal employment. It is marketed as flexible and accessible, but in reality, it is regulated and controlled by algorithms of platforms and indirectly also through migration policies.

The work itself offers opportunities for migrants who are confronted with limited access to the formal labour market such as rejected asylum seekers, labour migrants without the right to work but also international students with limited rights to formal employment ([Salamena 2025](#)). At the same time, the recruitment of migrants who have recently arrived in a country and whose legal status is insecure can also be framed as strategic exploitation of individuals who are inexperienced and with strong aspirations to enter the labour market. Account-sharing practices, informal subcontracting chains, **non-standard forms of employment and semi-formal arrangements**, and the role of 'fleet partners' create layers of dependency that replicate hierarchies of legality and status ([van Liempt & Hajer 2025](#), [Homel & Grzymala-Kazłowska 2025](#)).

Access to worker's rights is difficult in the platform economy that is driven by flexibility, quick profit and where customers' needs are prioritised over workers' rights. In some I-CLAIM countries we observed that police checks and digital ID systems around food delivery work extend immigration enforcement into the workplace which makes the sector an even more risky place to work for irregular migrants ([Sigona et al. 2025](#)).

MAIN FINDING #4:**Alongside patterns of dependency, I-CLAIM research documents a range of forms of resistance and organising amongst irregularised workers**

Irregularised workers engage in everyday acts of navigation and mobility – changing employers, sharing information amongst workers about untrustworthy employers, or forming informal support networks – to navigate hostile systems. Due to the isolated nature of the work, and the demanding nature of the jobs, workers have little or no opportunity to organise their lives outside work or to socialise. Accordingly, it was found to be very difficult to mobilise for irregularised workers.

We did find a few examples of collective mobilisation, often in collaboration with trade unions, migrant associations, and civil-society organisations that offer advice, solidarity, and political visibility. Delivery riders organised through digital channels to warn each other and protest unfair working conditions. For domestic workers we came across networks and grassroots unions in Italy and the UK that have linked struggles for recognition to broader campaigns for social rights. In the Netherlands a small group of domestic workers is represented in the trade union FNV. NGOs across all I-CLAIM countries also provide spaces of protection and collective voice that support irregularised migrant workers. These initiatives reveal how, even under restrictive regimes, irregularised migrants exercise agency and contribute to evolving forms of social organisation around work and rights.

Policy recommendations

POLICY RECOMMENDATION #1:**Expand and improve labour migration and regularisation pathways**

I-CLAIM research shows that irregularised migrants are dominant in sectors of the economy characterised by informality, weak regulation, and exploitation, reflecting the barriers they face when trying to access formal employment, such as restrictive asylum policies, limited labour migration pathways, lack of skills recognition, discrimination and language barriers.

Throughout Europe, accessible and decent labour migration pathways across skills and sectors remain very limited, despite labour market demand. Mechanisms such as quotas, shortage occupation lists, and labour market tests are implemented in a way that blocks - or creates over-burdensome administrative hurdles to - the employment of migrant workers in key occupations. This leads to fragmentation of the labour market and contributes to more undeclared work ([PICUM, 2021](#)). Single employer-tied permits are of particular concern, creating the conditions for dependency and exploitation ([Weatherburn, 2023](#)).

At the same time, regularisation pathways should be put place, given that most European countries only have complex, discretionary and limited or temporary regularisation mechanisms in place. EU legal instruments—such as the [Seasonal Workers Directive](#)—should be revised so that they also apply to irregularised migrants already present in Member States.

It is, therefore, recommended to:

- Ensure an adequate duration of work and residence permits and simplify the procedure for permits by making the applications and renewals more accessible.
- Reduce the dependency on the employer, including the right to change employer or seek alternative employment given a reasonable amount of time.
- Transitional permits should be available to workers who have experienced exploitation, to enable them to stabilise their situation without falling into irregularity.
- In cases of severe labour right violations, irregularised workers should be granted residence permits under national law, in order to enable the effective exercise of victims' rights guaranteed by the [Victims' Rights Directive](#) (see also [PICUM, 2022](#)), the [Employers' Sanctions Directive](#) and the [Anti-Trafficking Directive](#). Such permits should ensure the right to stay and work independently of cooperation with law enforcement or judicial authorities, and provide pathways to longer-term residence.
- Member States and the UK should establish clear, transparent and permanent mechanisms for regularising the status of people currently living in an irregular situation given that most European countries only have complex, discretionary and limited or temporary regularisation mechanisms in place.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION #2:

Regulate subcontracting and labour intermediation

The increasing use of long and complex subcontracting chains for core business operations, persistent undeclared or semi-formal and non-standard work contracts and of fraudulent labour intermediation are key drivers of labour exploitation, undermining workers' rights, decent work and collective bargaining. These practices enable companies and individuals to blur responsibility for compliance with workers' and trade union rights, employment standards and collective agreements as well as occupational health and safety rules. This is especially the case in fraud-sensitive sectors such as agriculture, cleaning and care work as well as food delivery work.

When workers get trapped in complex chains, liability becomes unclear and enforcement nearly impossible. In many cases, migrant workers do not know who their actual employer is, resulting in weakened bargaining power and protection of their rights. These dynamics often involve complex and opaque subcontracting structures, which are encouraged by weak or non-existent liability schemes. This leads to fragmented and unclear rules, responsibilities and obligations, thereby creating conditions that facilitate² and labour exploitation.³

Existing EU rules on labour migration, mobility, posting, temporary agency work and occupational health and safety do not effectively tackle the emergence of business models whereby companies and individuals engage in chains of intermediaries and subcontractors to reduce costs and evade responsibility. For this reason:

³ See, for instance, L. Palumbo (forthcoming), *Tackling undeclared work among third-country nationals: trends and challenges for the enforcement authorities*, Discussion Paper, ELA. P. Van Nierop, L. Schönenberg, P. Petar Terziev, with contributions from A. Besic, K. Jakubowska, N. Rose, R. Stefanov, D. Mineva (2021), *Counteracting undeclared work and labour exploitation of third-country national workers*, European Platform tackling undeclared work, p. 37-38.

- Private labour market intermediaries should be regulated and monitored for compliance, including to ensure that [recruitment](#) fees and related costs are not paid directly or indirectly by workers.
- Establish EU-level rules for transparent registration and oversight of intermediaries operating in high-risk sectors, increase transparency and legal accountability across jurisdiction and within supply chains. Rules should be established through an evidence-based and multi-stakeholder process.
- The introduction of an [EU-wide legal framework](#) to limit subcontracting and ensure joint and several liability throughout the subcontracting chain is essential. An EU Directive is needed to promote direct employment relations, secure equal treatment with full respect for workers' rights and employment standards, effective enforcement, transparency and accountability across sectors, including in the platform economy. The upcoming Quality Jobs Roadmap and Act provides with a key opportunity to tackle this issue at European level.
 - Guarantee that, in cases where accommodation is provided by a subcontractor or an intermediary, it is organised independently from the employment contract to avoid any associated further dependency on the employer. Equally, Member States shall ensure that the termination of one contract does not automatically entail the termination of the other contract.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION #3:

Ensure access to justice and effective complaint mechanisms

The principle that a worker is a worker, regardless of immigration or residence status should be upheld. Irregularised workers despite formal entitlements under EU law are reluctant to exercise their rights before national labour enforcement authorities due to the ever-present fear of deportation. The upcoming revision of the European Pillar of Social Rights Action Plan provides a timely opportunity to embed migrant workers' rights at the heart of EU social policy, ensuring that fair working conditions and fundamental labour rights are not dependent on immigration status ([SOLIDAR, 2025](#)). Effective labour protections and complaint mechanisms require [firewalls](#) between labour enforcement and immigration control, applicable to all workers regardless of immigration status.

- Confidential, effective and accessible complaint mechanisms should be established for all workers, regardless of immigration or residence status. Enable trade unions and civil society actors to represent claimants, and permitting civil society and human rights organisations to report violations and support victims throughout judicial proceedings.
- At national level, labour inspectorates should be enabled to effectively monitor high-risk sectors characterised by informality and labour exploitation including decent housing conditions, in line with the [ILO labour inspection convention, 1947 \(No 81\)](#). For domestic work, States that have not yet done so (e.g. the Netherlands and the UK) should ratify the [ILO's 2011 Domestic Work Convention No. 189](#) to facilitate inspections within private homes.
- Where present, sector-specific collective agreements should be better monitored and enforced to ensure employer compliance, including decent housing standards.
- Labour inspectors should receive training to identify labour exploitation and abuse and inform workers on their rights and possibility to claim for compensation and access residence permits. In this sense, [the FRA training manual on workplace inspectors](#) should serve as a practical tool, as well as the FRA and the European Labour Authority [guidelines for labour inspectors to identify labour exploitation](#).

- Labour migration policies should be evaluated for compliance with international labour standards particularly the [ILO core conventions](#).
- Acknowledging the legal enforceability of an employment relationship and/or contract involving a migrant worker in an irregular situation.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION #4:**Ensure access to information and support to irregularised workers**

- Irregularised workers should be informed with information on their labour rights, adequate accommodation and how to assert them in case of exploitation, for example with the support from trade unions and/or civil society organisations.
- Guarantee that irregularised workers are informed about their rights and have access to counselling, legal assistance, and interpretation services, whether provided directly by public authorities or through cooperation with social partners and civil society organizations.
- Strengthen the role of trade unions and civil society in defending irregularised workers' rights.
 - Ensure adequate funding both at EU and national level for trade unions and civil society organisations to reach and represent irregularised workers.
 - Ensure that the information is provided in the workers' own language or a language they understand and in a clear and transparent manner, regardless of the duration of their contract
 - The provision of information concerning working conditions should at least respect the minimum standards set by the Directive on transparent and predictable working conditions.

Annex: I-CLAIM Sector Reports

Agrifood

- **FINLAND:** Merikoski, P., and Näre, L. (2025) *Precarity and informality in agricultural food production in Finland: the role of migrant workers*. I-CLAIM. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/15775571>
- **GERMANY:** Salamena, B.B. (2025). *Living and Working Conditions of migrant seasonal workers in agriculture in Germany*. I-CLAIM. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/15775486>
- **ITALY:** Palumbo, L. (2025) *Women migrant workers with precarious legal status in the agricultural sector in Southern Italy*. I-CLAIM. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15833919](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15833919)
- **POLAND:** Matuszczyk, K. (2025) *Migrant labour in the Polish agriculture sector*. I-CLAIM. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/15780736>

Carework and cleaning

- **FINLAND:** Merikoski, P., and Näre, L. (2025) *Precarious migrants in domestic cleaning work. Findings from Finland*. I-CLAIM. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/15775520>
- **ITALY:** Marchetti, S., and Lashchuk, I. (2025) *Irregularised migrant domestic workers in Naples, Italy*. I-CLAIM. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/15775615>
- **NETHERLANDS:** Hajer, M., & van Liempt, I. (2025). *Irregular migrants in the Dutch Domestic Work Sector*. I-CLAIM. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15775196>
- **UNITED KINGDOM:** Sigona, N., Piemontese, S., Mendes, S.S., Achi, A. (2025) *Irregularised migrants doing domestic work in the United Kingdom*. I-CLAIM. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/15775346>

Logistics and delivery

- **GERMANY:** Salamena, B.B. (2025). *Irregularised migrants in the Delivery Sector (Berlin)*. I-CLAIM. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/15775449>
- **NETHERLANDS:** van Liempt, I., & Hajer, M. (2025). *Irregular migrants and precarity in the Dutch Food Delivery sector*. I-CLAIM. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/15775098>
- **POLAND:** Homel, K., & Grzymala-Kazłowska, A. (2025). *Living and working conditions of migrants in the delivery sector in Poland*. I-CLAIM. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15780657>
- **UNITED KINGDOM:** Sigona, N., Piemontese, S., Achi, A., Mendes, S.S. (2025) *Irregularised migrant workers in the UK food delivery sector*. I-CLAIM. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/15775291>

Comparative reports

- **Gender and households:** Näre, L., Merikoski & P., Colombi, D. (2026). *Gender and family dimensions of irregularised migrants' experiences and rights*. I-CLAIM. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18934192>
- **Labour sectors:** van Liempt, I., Grzymala-Kazłowska, A., Matuszczyk, K., & Palumbo, L. (2026). *Immigration Status and Labour Conditions Migrant workers in Agriculture, Delivery and Logistics, and Domestic and Care Work in Europe*. I-CLAIM. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18539025>
- **Racial logics of irregular migration:** Piemontese, S., Sigona, N., Lessard-Phillips, L., & Achiri, E.. (2026). *Racial logics of irregular migration in Europe*. I-CLAIM. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18693465>

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